
INTELLECTUAL CONTROL MODULES IN TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES

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Annotation: In the embedded controller architecture, a personal computer (PC) is used as a hardware platform for motion control. It allows to plan and control the multi-functional movement of control modules and systems, to perform information and measurement data processing functions in one device.

Key words: RS-232C, controller, computer, heat, vibration, transistor, interface, discrete.

Introduction.

Intelligent Management Modules, or IMS, modules aim to provide programming and management tools to add intelligent support to systems and computer networks. These are modules, intellectual promises, technologies that help you work safely and quickly for learning and decision-making.

IMS, depending on the size of the product, supports important modules that load on many external interfaces and perform similar basic functions. These modules include the following functions:

Precision Systems: IMS develops precision systems for developing machines. It helps to identify systems, defects and solve problems.

Remote Analysis: IMS is used to support network analysis. It helps in analysis, technology problem and error detection and troubleshooting.

Data Disclosure: IMS provides data disclosure, including management and reporting capabilities.

Decision Making: IMS provides support for survey creation, data analysis and automation of decision making processes.

Remote Learning: IMS supports network analysis and remote learning algorithms to augment learning.

Rework and Repair: IMS provides automatic repair and rework functions to identify problems and defects in systems and fix them quickly and reliably.

Intelligent control modules help in mastering systems, increasing security and optimizing systems. They create wide opportunities for improving product quality, improving service quality and developing systems.

Planning of functional activities is carried out by an operator on a high-level computer with the help of application software packages. In addition, the computer automatically generates tasks sent to the controller through a standard interface (m-n, RS-232C). These tasks show the regularity of changes in the required position, speed and acceleration of the executive motor shaft over time.

From the user's point of view, the advantages of this are the integration of common operating systems and software tools (AutoCAD, Excel, Windows NT/95/3.1, C++, etc.) with motion programming systems. The integration of control computers in one network makes it possible to create distributed control complexes for the automation of cells, workshops and enterprises. In this case, the module structure in the PC protects the hardware from heat, vibration and other effects of production.

Built-in controllers are produced as special boards (plug-in cards) connected to an additional port of the computer. Data exchange between the controller and the PC is carried out through a simple (32-bit) bus of addresses and data. Common bus standards can be ISA, STD, VME and IBM-PC Bus. At the same time, the controller board has the necessary connector places for the driving power converter, feedback sensor (analog and digital), and external discrete input/output.

Intellectual power modules

We will consider ways and means of intellectualization of control modules aimed at integration of motion controllers and powerful converters. Such solutions are suitable for multi-dimensional control systems where the components are located at a large distance from each other. In this case, it will be difficult or technically impossible to implement the control system on one computer base. Because it is technically impossible to transmit and receive signals over long distances (for example, the simple RS-232 protocol can only transmit data and signals over a distance of 9.15 m).

In such systems, the control unit of each module is installed in the converter housing or in the terminal box of the electric motor. We call such modules intellectual power modules (IKM).

IKMs are made on the basis of new generation semiconductor devices. Typical manifestations of such devices are field-strength transistors (MOSFET), bipolar transistors (IGBT), field-controlled closing thyristors (MST). The new generation of devices has high speed (switching frequency for IGBT transistors up to 50 kHz, for MOSFET transistors - 100 kHz) and switching current and voltage (limit current for

IGBT - up to 1200 A, limit voltage - up to 3500 V) and small control power is distinguished by.

In addition to traditional devices of power electronics (switches built on the basis of powerful transistors or thyristors and diodes), IKM also includes elements of microelectronics. They are designed to perform intellectual functions: traffic control, protection in emergency mode and fault diagnosis. The use of IKMs in the driving part of control modules makes it possible to significantly reduce the mass and dimensions of powerful transformers, increase their reliability and improve their technical and economic indicators.

Figure 1 Intellectual control modules

Conclusions.

Intelligent Management Modules (IMS) are designed to provide programming and management tools for intelligent management of networks and systems. IMS helps to automate intelligent processes, learning and decision-making. They include key functions such as detection systems, remote analysis, data disclosure, decision making, remote learning, processing and repair. IMS helps in systems mastering, security enhancement and systems optimization. They provide a wide range of opportunities for improving product quality, improving service quality and developing systems.

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